

GLOBAL INTERNET TARMOG'IDAGI TAHDIDLARNING MAZMUN-MOHİYATI.

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Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrası o'qtuvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ma'naviy va axborot xurujlari kuchaygan davrda yashayapmiz. Bunday sharoitda tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishda huquq ta'limi ko'mak vazifasini bajaradi. Bunga ko'plab dalillarni keltirib o'tamiz.

Kalit so'z: internet, global, tahdid, xavf-xatar.

THE MEANING AND ESSENCE OF THREATS IN THE GLOBAL INTERNET NETWORK.

Abstract. We live in an era of increased spiritual and information attacks. In such conditions, Legal Education acts as a support in combating threats. Let's cite a lot of evidence for this.

Keyword: internet, global, threat, risk.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ УГРОЗ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ СЕТИ ИНТЕРНЕТ.

Аннотация. Мы живем в эпоху усиления моральных и информационных атак. В этих условиях юридическое образование выступает в качестве поддержки в борьбе с угрозами. Мы приводим множество доказательств этого.

Ключевое слово: интернет, глобальный, угроза, риск.

Bugungi kunda ma'rifiy adabiyotlarda "ma'naviy tahdidlar" tushunchasi keng ishlatib kelinmoqda. Avvalo bu tushunchaning mohiyatini anglab olish zarur. Ma'naviy tahdidlar - shaxs axloqiy ongida salbiy tushunchalar, tuyg'ular, xususiyatlar va sifatlarni hosil qiluvchi illatlar majmuidir. Chunki "tahdid" so'zi xavf-xatar, xuruj va buzish ma'nolarini anglatadi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviy tahdidlar shaxsni aqliy va axloqiy jihatdan buzishga qaratilgan maqsadli xurujlar hisoblanadi.

Hozirgi davrda jamiyat barqarorligini izdan chiqarishga qaratilgan tahdidlar va ularning oldini olish muammolarini tadqiq etish muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Zero, so'nggi yillarda global miqyos kasb etib jamiyatning barcha sohalarini qamrab olayotgan turli xavf-xatarlar vujudga keldi, ularning oldini olishning samarali yo'llarini aniqlash ustuvor vazifaga aylandi.

Jumladan, internetning ijtimoiy-falsafiy tahlili; zamonaviy jamiyatda internetdan foydalanish madaniyati va internetdagi taxdidlarning kirib kelishi, tuzilishi va ijtimoiy vazifalari talqini kabi yo'nalishlarda tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Rivojlangan davlatlardagi tadqiqot markazlari va institutlari tomonidan internetning rivojlanish bosqichlari, vaqtlar o'tishi bilan ijobiy tomonlaridan ko'ra salbiy jixatlarining ko'payishi va kelajak avlod tarbiyasiga jiddiy zarar yetkazish xolatlariga aloxida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Bunday tahdidlarni oldini olish maqsadida mamlakatimizda milliy madaniyat va ma'naviyatni yuksaltirish masalalariga a'loxida e'tibor berib kelinmoqda. Milliy qadriyatlarimizni tiklash, milliy san'at va ijod sohasida katta o'zgarishlar ro'y bermoqda. Bu ishlarni amalga oshirish yo'lida Respublika Ma'naviyat targ'ibot markazi hamda Milliy g'oya va mafkura ilmiy-amaliy markazi tashkil etildi. 2017 yilda mazkur tashkilotlar birlashtirilib, ular negizida Respublika

Ma'aviyat va ma'rifat markazi tashkil etildi. Bu ishlarning faolligini yangi bosqichga ko'tarish maqsadida O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha 2017-2021 yillarga mo'ljallangan harakatlar strategiyasining qabul qilinishi yurtimizda milliy madaniyat yuksaloyotgani hamda turli taxdidlarning oldini olish borasida keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilayotganidan dalolat beradi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2016 yil 14 sentabrdagi "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida"gi Qonuni, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 28 iyuldagi PQ – 3160-son "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish va soxani rivojlantirishni yangi bosqichga ko'tarish to'g'risida"gi va 2019 yil 3 maydagi PQ – 4307-son "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'rsida"gi qarorlari hamda mavzuga oid boshqa meyoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarda belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirishga mazkur dissertatsiya tadqiqoti muayyan darajada xizmat qiladi.

XXI asrga kelib turli oqimlar va kuchlar tomonidan inson ongi va qalbi uchun kurash yanada avj oldi.

Hozirgi tahlikali zamonda internet tarmog'i orqali tarqatilayotgan g'arazli ma'lumotlar, turli buzg'unchi g'oyalar, odob-axloqni yemiruvchi manfur illatlar har bir ongli kishini tashvishga solishi aniq.

Internet yordamida ishlar oson va tez bajariladi. Lekin keyingi paylarda internet bilan bog'liq buzg'unchiliklar, global tarmoqdan qabih maqsadda foydalanayotganlar ko'payib bormoqda. Oqibatda, zalolatga boshlovchi elektron nashrlar va videolavhalar keng yoyilmoqda. Asosiy muammo internetdan kim qanday maqsadda foydalanayotgan ko'payib bormoqda. Oqibatda, zalolatga boshlovchi elektron nashrlar keng yoyilmoqda.

Asosiy muammo internetdan kim qanday maqsadda foydalanishida. Xozir yosh bola xam kompyuterni bemalol ishlata oladi. Bir qarashda, buning yomon joyi yo'qday. Ammo haddan oshilsa, nazorat bo'shshsa, oqibati juda yomon bo'ladi.

Internetga kirayotgan yoshlar soni soat sayin ortmoqda. Bir muxim ma'lumot: "Bolalarni asraylik" (Save the Children) xalqaro tashkiloti AQShdagi 15-17 yashar o'smirlarning 85 foizi, Kanada yoshlarining 93 foizi internetdan muntazam foydalanishini e'lon qildi.

O'zbekistonda internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni 2008 yilda 2 million, 2014 yilda 10 million bo'lgan bo'lsa hozir 22.1 milliondan oshgani, ularning aksariyati yoshlar ekanini alohida qayd etish kerak.

Mamlakatimizning birinchi Prezidenti "Bugungi kunda noan'anaviy tahdidlar xalqaro mojarolarning qiyofasini butunlay o'zgartirmoqda va informatsion-psixologik xurujlar sezilarli xavf-xatar tug'dirmoqda. Ular armiyamizning negiziga putur yetkazish, avvalo, uning ma'naviy-axloqiy asoslariga ta'sir o'tkazishga urinish va shuningdek, zamonaviy internet texnologiyalardan foydalanish orqali bizning bunyodkorlik ruhidagi boy madaniyatimiz, ma'naviy qadriyat va an'analarimizga mutlaqo zid bo'lgan buzg'unchi g'oya va tushunchalarni yoshlarimizning ongu tafakkuriga singdirishga qaratilgani bilan ayniqsa xatarlidir" deb ta'kidlagan. Tahdidlar va ularga qarshi kurashish zarurati ekologik muammolardan ham dolzarbroq ahamiyatga ega bo'lib bormoqda.

Birinchi Prezidentimiz "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida ta'kidlanganidek, " ...ma'naviyatga qarshi qaratilgan har qanday tahdid o'z-o'zidan mamlakat xavfsizligini, uning

milliy manfaatlarini, sogʻlom avlod kelajagini taʼminlash yoʻlidagi jiddiy xatarlardan biriga aylanishi va oxir oqibatda jamiyatni inqirozga olib kelishi mumkin” .

Biz gʻoyaviy, maʼnaviy va axborot xurujlari kuchaygan davrda yashayapmiz. Bunday sharoitda tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishda huquq taʼlimi koʻmak vazifasini bajaradi. Bunga koʻplab dalillarni keltirib oʻtamiz.

Birinchidan, hali voyaga yetmagan 2 yoshli bola issiq choynakda barmogʻini bexosdan bir marotaba kuydirib olsa, u choynakdan yiroq yuradi. Biroq, onasi sovutib bergan piyolaning suvini istagancha toʻkaveradi, piyolani sindirishga urinadi.

Bu qiyos bir qaraganda ilmiy qiyosga oʻxshamaydi. Ammo bildirmoqchi boʻlgan fikrimiz butunlay boshqa. Biz huquqqa hurmat tuygʻusi va mafkuraviy immunitetni eng avvalo oilada, mahallada, maktabgacha, umumiy oʻrta, oʻrta-maxsus va kasb-hunar taʼlimi muassasalarida shakllantirish orqali tahdidlarning har qanday turiga qarshi kurasha olamiz.

Ikkinchidan, yuqoridagi fikrning davomi sifatida taʼkidlash lozimki, tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishning huquqiy asoslari taʼlim muassasalaridagi darslik va oʻquv qoʻllanmalarida yetarlicha yoritilmayapti.

Uchinchidan, mavjud oʻquv adabiyotlarida mehnat qilish va oila qurish yoshi koʻrsatilgan. Yoshlarimiz bu toʻgʻrisida maʼlumot olishlari ijobiy holat. Biroq, taʼlim muassasasidagi oʻqishga taʼsir etadigan mehnat sharoitlarida ishlash mumkin emasligini ularga yetkazib berish pedagoglar oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan biridir. Oila kodeksiga koʻra, Oila qurishga yigitlarga 18 yoshdan, qizlarga esa 17 yoshdan yoʻl qoʻyilar edi. Emanspatsiya holatiga koʻra bu raqamlar yana bir yilga qisqarishi mumkin edit. Ushbu yoshda voyaga yetmaganlarning taʼlim muassasasida tahsil olayotganligiga ham eʼtiborimizni qaratishimiz lozim. Bu holat yigit va qizlarimizning taʼlim muassasasidagi faoliyatiga salbiy taʼsirini oʻtkazar edi. Qonunchilikdagi oʻzgarishlarga muvofiq nikoh yoshining tenglashtirilishi bu muammoning yechimi boʻldi.

REFERENCES

1. Мўйдинов, А. (2021). ЁШЛАРНИ ТУРЛИ ТАҲДИДЛАРДАН ҲИМОЯ ҚИЛИШДА АЖДОДЛАР МЕРОСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 132-137.
2. Asilbek, M. (2022). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION OF AN ENLIGHTENED PERSON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Conferencea*, 183-186.
3. Adham oʻgʻli, M. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL WITCHCRAFT HERITAGE IN THE SPIRITUAL RISE OF SOCIETY (SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS). *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 122-127.
4. Muydinov, A. (2022). ENLIGHTENMENT IN TURKESTAN IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX-EARLY XX CENTURIES. ENLIGHTENMENT BY JADID SCHOOL. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 14-20.
5. Ruzmatovich, U. S. (2022). PROCESSES OF ORGANIZATION OF TECHNICAL, TACTICAL AND PHYSICAL PREPARATION IN NATIONAL WRESTLING TRAINING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT,*

- ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 65-68.*
6. Ruzmatovich, U. S. (2022). CHANGES EXPECTED TO COME IN OUR LIFE MOVEMENTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(3), 485-489.
 7. Shohbozjon, K., & Azizjon, M. (2022). PREPARING SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS BEFORE ENTRY TO HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(10), 100-108.*
 8. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Developing Critical Thinking In Primary School Students. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
 9. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
 10. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.
 11. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). Methodical Support Of Development Of Creative Activity Of Primary School Students. *Conferencea*, 74-76.
 12. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
 13. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
 14. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
 15. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
 16. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., Oljayevna, O. F., Qizi, T. D. T., Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Anvarovna, A. O. (2020). Pedagogical Features Of Mental Development Of Preschool Children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 14221-14225.
 17. Sharofutdinova, R. I., Asadullaev, A. N., & Tolibova, Z. X. (2021). The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 2(5), 376-379.
 18. Iqboljon, S. (2022). Boshlang'ich Sinf o'quv Jarayonida Axborot Texnologiyalaridan Foydalanish. *Ijodkor o'qituvchi*, 2(20), 137-140.
 19. Iqboljon, S. (2022). KOMPYUTER YORDAMIDA DARSLARNI TASHKIL ETISH. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 1(9), 246-249.
 20. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 424-429.
 21. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). THE ACTUAL STATUS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN

- THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(12), 206-213.
22. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). BO ‘LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINING AMALIYOTDA QOLLASH. Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 2(7), 54-58.
 23. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK FANLARNING BO ‘LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI O ‘RNI. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(6), 17-24.
 24. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA‘LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO ‘LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK TIZIMI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 2(14), 13-19.
 25. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA‘LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO ‘LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MODEL. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(13), 77-84.
 26. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION INFORMATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(4), 574-580.
 27. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). FORMS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON THE ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF INFORMATIZATION OF EDUCATION. *Science and innovation*, 2(B3), 5-8.
 28. Usmonjon o‘g‘li, S. I. (2022). TA‘LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNALOGIYA. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 120-128.
 29. Абдужабборов, А., & Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИДА ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ҚАРАТИЛГАН ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ.
 30. Sharofutdinova, R., & Abduqodirov, B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 904-910.
 31. Sharafutdinova, R., & Abdujabborov, A. (2023). EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 890-896.
 32. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). ИЖОД ТУШУНЧАСИ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМИ. *O‘ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 854-861.
 33. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ-ИЖТИМОЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТ СИФАТИДА. *O‘ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 842-847.
 34. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуқодиров, Б. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ

- РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ ВА ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 862-868.
35. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдужабборов, А. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАНЛИГИДА ҲАМКОРЛИК КЛАСТЕРИ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 848-853.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Sohiboxon, S. (2023). MAXSUS TA'LIMNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 830-836.
37. Ra'noxon, S., Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(11), 881-885.
38. Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(11), 213-217.
39. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., & O'ljayevna, O. R. F. (2020). Tursunova Dilnavoz To 'lqin qizi, Sharofutdinova Ra'noxon Shavkatovna, Ashurova Oygul Anvarovna. Pedagogical features of mental development of preschool children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6).
40. Mirzaxolmatovna, X. Z., Nematovna, R. S., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2022). FORMS OF THINKING IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING MATHEMATICS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 259-263.
41. Ganiev, A. A., Abdullaev, S. Y., & Abdurahmonov, S. Z. (2021). Combined treatment for early-stage skin cancer of the head and neck area. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 4, 3-6.
42. Ganiev, A. A., & kizi Ganieva, O. O. TASAVVUF TARIQATI YO 'NALISHLARI VA NAQSHBANDIYA TARIQATINING O 'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.
43. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Uzbekistan's General Education School Physical Education Programme: A Curriculum Analysis. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 184-193.
44. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Examining the First Age Group's Health Test Needs for "Salomatlik" Regulation Using the Dynamic of Children's Motor Potential. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 194-200.
45. Kosimov, K., & Mamayusupov, J. (2019). Transitions melline integral of fractional integrodifferential operators. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(1), 12-15.
46. Qo'Ziyev, S. S., & Mamayusupov, J. S. (2021). Umumiy o 'rta ta'lim maktablari uchun elektron darslik yaratishning pedagogik shartlari. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 447-453.
47. Мамаюсупов, Ж. Ш. (2022). Интегральное преобразование Меллина для оператора интегродифференцирования дробного порядка. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11, 186-188.
48. Mamayusupov, J. S. O. (2022). "IQTISOD" YO 'NALISHI MUTAXASSISLARINI TAYYORLASHDA МАТЕМАТИКА FANINI O 'QITISH USLUBIYOTI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(3), 720-728.

49. Mamayusupov, J., & Sattarov, A. (2022). Mellin Integral Replacement and its Applications. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 15, 256-263.
50. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). PISA XALQARO BAHOLASH TIZIMI VA UNING MATEMATIK AHAMIYATI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 25(1), 3-8.
51. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). MATEMATIK MODEL VA MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING UMUMIY PRINSIPLARI. *World scientific research journal*, 13(1), 45-48.
52. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
53. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 176-182.
54. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
55. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGUISTICS AND THE HISTORY OF ITS ANALYTICAL DEVELOPMENT. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 99-105.
56. Vosiljonov, A., & Isaqova, X. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(2).
57. KHALIMBOYEVA, F., & VOSILJONOV, A. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR DIQQATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOSINI NAZARIY O'RGANILISHI. *Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies*, 1(5), 94-98.
58. Soxibov, S. (2023). THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IS A HUGE TASK. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1037-1041.
59. Soxibov, S. (2023). MEASURES TO FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1031-1036.
60. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL-ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND PREVENTION OF CORRUPT RELATIONS. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
61. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2021, April). THE ROLE OF RELIGIOUS AND MORAL EDUCATION IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION, ALONG WITH THE USE OF ECONOMIC AND LEGAL FACTORS. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 55-57).
62. Нажмиддинов, Э., & Мухамедиев, М. (2023). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
63. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., & Мухаммадиев, М. А. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИНИНГ ТУР ТАРКИБИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 60-68.
64. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 189-194.
65. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NATURE IN THE FORMATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE IDEAL GENERATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 149-154.

66. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). " ICHTHYOLOGY AND HYDROBIOLOGY" PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 152-160.
67. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE NEED TO IMPROVE HUMAN'S NOOSPHERICAL RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 23-30.
68. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING PERSONAL ECOLOGICAL CULTURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 5-12.
69. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). АТРОФ-МУҲИТНИ АСРАШ БЎЙИЧА МИЛЛИЙ СТРАТЕГИК РЕЖА ВА УНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 251-258.
70. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). ЯНГИ ТАРАҚҚИЁТ БОСҚИЧИДА ЭКОЛОГИК МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ДАСТУРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 1179-1186.
71. Абдумаликов, А. А. (2019). Human and Natural Harmony in the Historical Process. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 205-209.
72. Abidzhanovich, A. A. (2020). Issues Of Formation Of Rationality In Relations Of Nature With Society. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 301-304.
73. Abdumalikov, A. A. (2019). Environmental Ecological Policy in Uzbekistan and Necessity Of Formation Of Rational Communication To Nature. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(9), 94-101.
74. Мирзобоев, Й. А. (2022). Тур Ўзгариш Чизиқлари Учта Бўлган, Гиперболик Қисмларининг Ҳаммаси Характеристик Учбурчаклардан Иборат Бўлган Бешбурчакли Соҳада Учинчи Тартибли Кўринишдаги Параболик-Гиперболик Тенглама Учун Битта Чегаравий Масала Ҳақида. *Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research*, 1(5), 363-366.
75. MIRZABOYEV, Y. BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QITUVCHILARINING МАТЕМАТИКА О 'QITISH METODIKASI. О 'RTA UMUMTA'LIM МАКТАБЛАРИДА МАТЕМАТИКА О 'QITISHNING MAQSADI. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 169-172.
76. Iminov, B. B. (2020). INNOVATIVE CULTURAL LINKS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(3), 263-270.
77. Iminov, B. B. (2019). A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO INNOVATIVE AND CULTURAL-RELATIONS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(5), 157-162.
78. Qizi, S. G. G. O. (2022). LINGUISTIC BASIS AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF TEACHING WORD MEANING TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 117-123.
79. Qizi, S. G. G., & Teshaboyevna, D. D. Methods Of Formation Of Independent Reading Skills In Primary School Pupils. *JournalNX*, 21-24.
80. Kizi, S. G. G. (2021). Formation Of Independent Reading Skills in Primary School Students. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 222-224.

81. Valijonovna, K. I., Rakhmatjonovich, T. D., & Mukhtoraliyevna, Z. S. (2022). Informational Technology at Education. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 262-266.
82. Akmaljonovna, A. Z. (2021). Methods of formation of independent reading skills in primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1425-1428.
83. Dehqonova, M., & Tagonova, G. (2022). The Importance of Didactic Games in Speech Therapy in the Development of Speech in Children with Autism and the Ability to Choose Effective Methods. *European Journal of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 133-137.
84. Dehqonova, M. (2022). BOLALARDAGI YOZUV BUZILISHLARI VA ULARDAGI DISGRAFIYADA O 'ZIGA XOS XATOLIKLARNI PAYDO BO 'LISH MEXANIZMI. *YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR*, 405-407.
85. Dehqonova, M., & Najmiddinova, N. (2022). ALOHIDA EHTIYOJGA EGA BO'LGAN BOLALARNING OILAGA MOSLASHISHI UCHUN MUHIM OMILLAR. *YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR*, 90-92.
86. Dehqonova, M. (2023). MAXSUS MAKTABDA DAKTIL NUTQINI O'QITISH-TADQIQOT OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *Наука и инновация*, 1(1), 39-40.
87. Qizi, D. M. S., & Qizi, R. G. X. (2022). METHODS OF STUDYING ADDITION AND SUBTRACTION OF TWO-DIGIT NUMBERS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 22, 61-67.
88. Dehqonova, M. S. Q., & Axmedova, U. Y. Q. (2023). BO 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARINI MATEMATIK SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH JARAYONIDA ULARNING TAFAKKURI, QOBILIYATI VA INTELLEKTUAL RIVOJLANISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4-2), 251-256.
89. Otazonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Botirov, K. A., Qaxxorova, B. A., Xudoynazarova, M. A., Abdulkarimova, N. A., ... & Ismoilova, E. M. (2022, December). Influence of thickness and temperature on photoelectric properties of p-CdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-CdSe heterostructures. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012001). IOP Publishing.
90. Otajonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Axmedov, T., Usmonov, Y., & Karimov, B. (2022, December). Photoelectric properties of solar cells based on pCdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-nCdSe heterostructures. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012062). IOP Publishing.
91. Abdulvakhidov, K., Li, Z., Abdulvakhidov, B., Soldatov, A., Otajonov, S., Ergashev, R., ... & Sitalo, E. (2023). Structure phase state and physical properties of YbMn_{1-x}Fe_xO₃ compositions. *Applied Physics A*, 129(3), 185.
92. Ahmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2021). Vatanim Surati. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 877-883.
93. Axmedova, U. (2022). On Certain Conditions Of Striking Coefficients Of Fourier Series To Zero. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 3-8.
94. Qizi, A. U. Y., & Qizi, A. M. U. B. (2021). Research On Hydronyms and Their Importance.
95. Umidaxon, A., & Gulirano, S. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINF MATEMATIKA DARSLARIDA AMALIY MASHQLAR YECHISH JARAYONIDA

- O'QUVCHILARNING FIKRLASH QOBILIYATINI OSTIRISH OMILLARI. *PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOYIY TADQIQOTLAR*, 2(5), 10-14.
96. Axmedov, O. U. B. O. G., & Qizi, A. U. Y. (2022). STEREOOMETRIYA BO'LIMI VA UNING BA'ZI AKSIOMALARIDAN KELIB CHIQUADIGAN NATIJALAR. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 127-133.
97. Axmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2022). XALQ OG 'ZAKI IJOD NAMUNALARINING BOSHLANG 'ICH SINIF DARSLIKLARIDA QO 'LLANISHI VA ULARNING MAZMUNYIY GURUHLANISHI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 345-351.
98. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). Educational Methods in Teaching the Russian Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 260-263.
99. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 138-145.
100. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING INNOVATIVE METHODS. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 132-135.
101. Erkinovna, N. S. (2023). RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN WORLD. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 284-295.
102. Rakhmatjonov Shokhjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN PROVIDING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF THE ATHLETE// INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. International scientific online conference. Canada. Part 2, 23.01.2022. 1-3
103. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //SPORTCHI PSIXOLOGIK SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR// GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ). Vol. 10, Issue 11, Nov.(2022). 117-121 pages.
104. QURBONOVA Saida Miralimjanovna, RAXMATJONOV Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //MAMLAKATIMIZ PSIXOLOGLARI ISHLARIDA SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATDA MUOMALA MUAMMOSINING TALQINI// Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies. Vol. 1. № 5, (2023). 99-103 pages.
105. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //SPEECH ISSUES IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS// IQRO JURNALI № 2. 04.2023. 503-511 betlar.
106. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li, Vosiljonov Azizbek Boxodirjon o'g'li //XORIY PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI// INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. Vol. 1. № 12, 2022. 39-47 pages.
107. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH – IJTIMOYIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA// International Journal of Economy and Innovation. Volume: 30. 2022. 66-70 pages.
108. Rakhmatjonov Shokhjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS// IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI. Vol. 2 No. 11 (2022). 215-221 betlar.
109. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi// American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, Vol. 3 No. 11 (2022). 256-259 pages.

110. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //TOLERANTLIK SHAKLLANAYOTGAN SHAXS MODELINING TAVSIFI// International scientific journal «MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH». VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 5 /2023. 761-764 pages.
111. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYADA MOTIVATSIYA TURLARI, NAZARIYALARI VA TAHLILI. *Научный Импульс*, 1(10), 665-670.
112. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF WAYS TO BUILD A SELF-SIMILAR SOLUTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 950-958.
113. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF PROCESSES WITH CONVECTIVE TRANSPORT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 941-949.
114. Kadirov, S. (2023). HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL MONUMENTS AND THEIR CONDITION IN FERGANA REGION (1991-2020 IN THE CASE OF THE CITY OF MARGILAN): THE ISSUE OF PRESERVATION, PROTECTION AND THEIR USE. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 818-830.
115. Abduraxmonov, A., & Kadirov, S. (2022). DEMOGRAFIK JARAYONLARNING IQTISODIY-IJTIMOYIY SOHALARNI RIVOJLANISHI BILAN BOG 'LIQLIGI VA DASTLABKI XUSUSIY MULK MASALALARI. *IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 222-229.
116. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODS FOR GROWING SPEECH SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1028-1030.
117. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE NOUN PHRASE CATEGORY: ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING IN STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1025-1027.
118. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2023). Superstitions in Linguoculturology. *DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY"*, 14(1).
119. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). O 'QUVCHILAR NUTQINI O 'STIRISH METODIKASI. *IQRO JURNALI*, 2(2), 637-645.
120. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING NUTQDAGI O'RNINI. *IQRO*, 2(2), 522-529.
121. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2022). ORIGIN AND CONCEPT OF TABOO VOCABULARY. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(10), 184-190.